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The Work-Life of PWD Teachers in Public Schools: A Transcendental Phenomenological Study

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the lived experiences of teachers with disabilities (PWD) in public schools in South Cotabato, Philippines. Utilizing a qualitative, transcendental phenomenological design, the research gathered data through in-depth interviews with five (5) PWD teachers. The study explored their work-life experiences, focusing on challenges, opportunities, and recommendations to improve their professional roles. The findings revealed six significant themes: Joys and Rewards, which highlighted the fulfillment PWD teachers find in seeing their students succeed; Struggles and Challenges, which included physical limitations and emotional struggles like isolation; Hopes for the Future, centered on aspirations for inclusive policies and accessible school environments; Challenges in the Workplace, such as inadequate infrastructure and lack of support systems; Opportunities and Growth, which emphasized the adaptability and empathy developed through their unique experiences; and Recommendations for Support, focusing on the need for assistive technologies, improved accessibility, and systemic reforms at school, district, and national levels. The study concluded that while PWD teachers demonstrate resilience and dedication, systemic barriers hinder their work-life experience. Recommendations include infrastructure improvements, inclusive training programs, and enhanced policy implementation to foster a supportive and equitable educational environment for PWD teachers. By addressing these factors, the Department of Education (DepEd) can promote greater inclusivity and empower PWD teachers as valued contributors to the Philippine education system.

Keywords: *PWD Teachers, phenomenological study, challenges, work-life*

Introduction

The experiences of teachers with disabilities (PWD) have long been overshadowed, signaling a pressing and often neglected issue within the academic landscape. This paper endeavors to shed light on the significant challenges faced by teachers with disabilities in the Philippines, a facet of education that has been conspicuously disregarded. Existing literature vividly portrays the hurdles these educators encounter, spanning discrimination, accessibility issues, and societal misconceptions. Notable studies, such as "A Narrative Analysis of the Experiences of Teachers with Disabilities in the Philippines" (San Jose, 2022) and "Facing the Challenge: Exposing Teachers with Disabilities Who Teach the Filipino Subject" (Ubani, 2023), spotlight the adversities faced by teachers with disabilities, underscoring the urgent need for a comprehensive understanding of their unique struggles.

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), approximately 15% of the global population (1 billion people) are persons with disabilities (PWDs), with 80% of them falling within working age categories (ILO). While PWDs can engage in various industries, they often confront higher unemployment rates, lower employment rates, and limited economic activity, placing them at risk of poverty (De Luna-Narido & Tacadao, 2016).

The 2030 Development Agenda emphasizes leaving no one behind, promoting private sector employment of PWDs to reduce inequalities and empower them (Bonaccio et al., 2019). The global context further amplifies the urgency of this exploration. Studies like "Barriers Globally Faced by Persons with Disabilities" (Ubani & Sanikpege, 2023) underscore the universal challenges confronted by PWDs, revealing attitudinal, physical, communication, policy, and economic barriers.

However, the Philippines, as a microcosm, introduces specific intricacies and nuances, outlined in research such as "The Voices that Cannot Be Heard: A Phenomenological Study on the Lived Experiences of Deaf Teachers" (Vicente, 2020) and "Understanding CRPD Implementation in the Philippines" (Cruz, 2017). These studies shed light on the localized challenges faced by teachers with disabilities in the Philippine education landscape, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions.

The Philippines is committed to promoting social justice and decent work for PWDs, with various policies, programs, and services in place (Jaucian, 2017). Despite existing laws and policies, barriers like poverty and access to basic services hinder the full inclusion of PWDs in Philippine society (Jaucian, 2017).

Moreover, the experiences of teachers with disabilities extend beyond the classroom, intertwining with broader societal issues. "The Lived Experience of Losing Employment after Diagnosis with Dementia" (Blaine, 2022) unveils the profound impact of job loss due to dementia, underlining the need for workplace inclusivity and support systems. Conversely, "A Productivity Assessment of PWD Employees in a Philippine Company" (Seva, 2020) challenges prevailing stereotypes by revealing the productivity and job satisfaction of PWDs in the workplace.

Teachers with disabilities can bring unique knowledge and serve as examples of important principles, like justice, independence, and tolerance (Anderson, 2006). Research is needed to understand the experiences, challenges, and opportunities of PWD teachers in the Philippines for improving their work life (San Jose, 2022).

As researcher navigate this intricate landscape, it becomes imperative to identify research gaps and articulate the aims of the investigation. Through a critical synthesis of the existing literature, this study aim to pinpoint areas that require further exploration and understanding. By examining the specific challenges faced by teachers with disabilities in the Philippines, this study sought to contribute to the on-going discourse on inclusive education and equitable work environments.

In addressing the underexplored narratives of teachers with disabilities (PWD) in the Philippines, this paper pursues a comprehensive understanding of their work lives within the public school system. Drawing on a rich tapestry of research, this study aimed to unravel the lived experiences of PWD teachers, capturing the challenges and triumphs that shape their professional journeys. Our exploration extends beyond the confines of the classroom, examining the broader societal implications and opportunities inherent in the work lives of these educators. Through a nuanced analysis, this study seek to identify actionable recommendations for improving the work life of PWD teachers in public schools in the Philippines, contributing to the on-going discourse on inclusive education and fostering a more supportive and equitable environment for educators with disabilities.

Research Questions

The study aimed to explore the lived experiences of PWD public teachers in South Cotabato, Philippines. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of PWD public teachers in South Cotabato, Philippines?
2. What are the challenges and opportunities that PWD teachers face in their work life?
3. What are the recommendations for improving the work life of PWD public teachers in South Cotabato, Philippines?

Literature Review

Live Experiences of PWD Teachers in the Philippines

The Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities (RA 7277) is a landmark legislation that guarantees the rights of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in the Philippines. It was signed into law on February 23, 1992, and has been instrumental in promoting the inclusion and well-being of PWDs in society. It was after a lot of research and because of their findings that this particular law has been crafted. However after 30 years there are still questions whether it has been fully implemented. And so there is a need to revisit the experiences of PWD's in the workplace today.

Almeda San Jose's study in 2022 offers a compelling narrative analysis of the experiences of teachers with disabilities in the Philippines. It provides an in-depth exploration of the challenges encountered by these educators, including discrimination from students, parents, and colleagues. The study also highlights the lack of necessary support from both the government and school administration, as well as the compounding difficulties of inaccessible workplaces and teaching materials.

However, it is important to note that the study also underscores the resilience and determination of these teachers, who serve as role models for their students and demonstrate that individuals with disabilities can succeed in any profession.

In a similar vein, Vicente's phenomenological study in 2020 focuses on a specific subgroup of PWD teachers, namely, Deaf teachers. This research reveals the unique challenges faced by Deaf teachers, including discrimination and communication barriers. Despite these challenges, the study highlights the passion for teaching and the support Deaf teachers receive, enabling them to excel in their roles. Their experiences empower them to challenge negative stereotypes and advocate for inclusive education practices.

Furthermore, Neca, Borges, and Pinto's literature review in 2022 provides a comprehensive overview of the common challenges experienced by teachers with disabilities. This literature review underscores recurring themes such as discrimination, a lack of support, and the difficulties associated with finding employment after completing their education. However, it also highlights the substantial contributions made by these educators to the education system, effectively dispelling stereotypes and reinforcing the idea that people with disabilities can excel in a wide array of professions.

Ubani's study in 2023 zeroes in on the specific challenges faced by teachers with disabilities who specialize in teaching the Filipino subject in Davao. This research not only highlights these challenges, which include discrimination, inaccessibility, and negative stereotypes, but it also showcases the resilience and resourcefulness of these teachers. They have developed an array of coping mechanisms to navigate the difficulties they encounter. Despite these obstacles, they remain steadfast in making substantial contributions to the education system in Davao, underscoring their unwavering dedication and determination.

Public school employees with disabilities in the Philippines grapple with discrimination, lack of accessibility, and a pervasive unawareness of the rights and needs of Persons with Disabilities (Avila et al., 2023). Despite these challenges, PWDs within public schools showcase remarkable resilience and determination, making significant contributions to the education sector.

Differently-abled public servants in Carmen, Davao del Norte, confront discrimination and various challenges in their roles, yet they persevere, making noteworthy contributions to public service (Mullot et al., 2021). The study provides valuable recommendations aimed at improving their work experiences.

Challenges and Opportunities of PWD Public Teachers

Exploring the challenges and opportunities integral to the professional lives of PWD (Persons with Disabilities) teachers provides a crucial lens for comprehending the dynamics of inclusive education and the broader employment landscape. A comprehensive overview of pertinent studies sheds light on the multifaceted nature of these aspects in PWD teachers' professional journeys.

In the realm of challenges, Almeda San Jose's narrative analysis (2022) unravels a spectrum of obstacles faced by PWD teachers in the Philippines. This includes prevalent discrimination from students, parents, and colleagues, coupled with insufficient support from the government and school administration. The challenges are further compounded by inaccessible workplaces, teaching materials, and negative stereotypes, collectively creating hurdles for PWD teachers in their professional roles. Vicente's phenomenological study (2020) underscores additional challenges faced by Deaf teachers, emphasizing communication barriers and discrimination that hinder effective engagement with students and colleagues. A broader perspective is provided by the literature review of Neca, Borges, and Pinto (2022), revealing common global challenges for teachers with disabilities, including discrimination, lack of support, and post-education employment difficulties.

Koca-Atabey's research in 2016 offers a comparative perspective by examining the journeys of individuals with visual impairments who aspire to become teachers. This study illuminates the considerable challenges they face, including discrimination, a lack of support, and accessibility issues. Nonetheless, these individuals emerge with robust professional identities, illustrating their resilience and determination as they make significant contributions to the field of education. These educators serve as inspirations for future generations and effectively challenge stereotypes.

On the other side, opportunities for PWD teachers are highlighted in several studies. Ubani's study (2023) acknowledges the challenges while emphasizing the resourcefulness and coping mechanisms employed by PWD teachers, showcasing their determination and resilience. Seva's productivity assessment (2020) challenges stereotypes by indicating that PWDs can be as productive as, or even surpass, their non-disabled counterparts. The study underscores the valuable contributions of PWDs to the workplace. Additionally, Brown & Jeffress's study (2018) illuminates an opportunity within the educational setting, showing that students exposed to instructors with disabilities reported more positive attitudes, suggesting a potential role for PWD teachers in fostering inclusivity and changing attitudes.

Cruz's research on "Understanding CRPD Implementation in the Philippines" (2017) provides a broader societal perspective. Despite persistent challenges, the study recommends raising awareness and implementing anti-discrimination laws to promote a more inclusive and equitable society, consequently creating opportunities for PWD teachers.

Individuals confronted with job loss after a dementia diagnosis undergoes a spectrum of emotions, including grief, loss, fear, uncertainty, and anger (Blaine, 2022). Negotiating financial hardship, job search struggles, and social isolation, participants find avenues to infuse their lives with meaning and purpose amidst adversity.

Student teachers with physical disabilities encounter hurdles such as negative stereotypes, a dearth of role models, and accessibility issues (Dvir, 2015). Despite these obstacles, these individuals emerge from the experience with robust professional identities, making substantial contributions to the teaching profession.

In the realm of work life for individuals with physical disabilities, a comparative study reveals that they often report lower work-life balance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Kotzé, 2008). The study emphasizes the pivotal role of accessibility, flexibility, and a supportive work culture in enhancing the quality of work life for people with disabilities.

Teachers' perspectives on inclusive education in Delhi, India, present a nuanced landscape with mixed attitudes, ranging from support to skepticism. There is a shared sentiment among teachers regarding the need for more training, resources, and support to effectively implement inclusive education practices in the educational landscape (Tiwari et al., 2015).

Methodology

Research Design

Transcendental Phenomenology, largely developed by Husserl, is a philosophical approach to qualitative research methodology seeking to understand human experience (Moustakas, 1994). This design makes it possible to thoroughly examine the struggles and experiences faced by numerous groups of PWD teachers within the Department of Education.

Participants

The researcher employed purposive sampling to determine the sampling strategy to comprehend the significance of PWD public teachers' lived experiences. In which players fulfil a predetermined requirement. The researchers sought subjects that have had an experience but differ in their qualities and personal experiences (Moser & Korstiens, 2017).

The principal participants of this study were the PWD public school teachers from various schools within South Cotabato with at least one-year teaching experience in the Department of Education. The researchers chose the five (5) teachers as the participants since they

qualify the criteria provided by the researchers.

Instrument

The researchers utilized guide questions, the guide questions contained questions that determined the live experiences of the PWD public teachers in order to gather the information needed for the study.

The participants were interviewed to respond to the given questions to determine and examine their experiences. With the permission from the participants, the researchers used an audio or a voice recorder to record the entire interview. The audio recording served as an aid in documenting the interview process and later will be used to transcribe the participants' responses.

The researchers did not record the participant's name or any other personal information on any of the materials they utilized. The study's records were included, which could potentially help identify the participants. All participant private and personal information was deleted at the end of the study. Participants have a significant role to play, as do the researchers. One right entails the obligation of the other. Researchers must respect the rights of research participants and take their viewpoints into account.

Procedure

To complete this study, the researchers followed a step by the step process to gathering the data needed. The researchers will request and seek the approval of the Principal of the school. They will also prepare a letter of approval addressed to the Principal. The content of the letter asks for approval to conduct interview with the teachers. After they received the approval from the principal and supervisor, the researchers will meet with the participants and present them with the approved endorsement letter from the principal. The researchers will ask for the schedule of the teachers for the conduct of the study. They will also give the interview guide to the participants for them to study and prepare.

Data Analysis

The researchers transcribed and translated the informants' talks, ensuring accuracy and clarity of the collected data. The study began by eliminating the researchers' subjectivity, setting aside any preconceptions or biases to approach the phenomenon with an open perspective. Data analysis followed a systematic process: first, horizontalization, where all significant phrases were identified and irrelevant or repetitive statements were removed, leaving only the essential horizons. Next, thematic clustering was conducted, wherein data were grouped into units of meaning, and clustered themes were formed to represent participants' experiences. The researchers then developed textural descriptions, creating narratives that depicted "what" participants experienced, followed by structural descriptions, explaining "how" the experiences occurred through creative analysis and interpretation. Finally, a synthesis of the textural and structural descriptions expressed both the "what" and "how" of the phenomenon, written from a third-person perspective to reflect the collective narratives of the group.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical requirements. Respondents freely participated. Care was taken to assure their safety and well-being: being, and that they had no physical, mental, social, or emotional impairment. There was always respect for the school head. Participants include stakeholders. The privacy of the information obtained.

Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed six (6) relevant themes, which were synthesized through initial themes, clustered themes, and formulated meanings.

These themes reflect the multifaceted nature of their experiences, incorporating elements of personal fulfilment, challenges, growth, and the need for systemic change. The themes identified were: Joys and Rewards, Struggles and Challenges, Hopes for the Future, Challenges in the Workplace, Opportunities and Growth, and Recommendations for Support. Below is an in-depth discussion of each relevant theme and how it reflects the lived experiences of PWD teachers.

Relevant Theme 1: Joys and Rewards

The theme of Joys and Rewards encapsulates the positive experiences that PWD (Persons with Disabilities) teachers find in their roles. Despite the difficulties associated with their disabilities, the participants emphasized the emotional and professional rewards they experience in teaching. Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Personal Fulfilment and Gratitude for Acceptance. These were derived from two initial themes such as "Making a difference in students' lives" and "Feeling valued and supported."

Most participants in the study expressed a profound sense of pride and joy from seeing their students succeed and grow. Participant 1 shared, "My joy comes from seeing my students, despite their own challenges, excel and grow. It's fulfilling to witness their success." This sentiment was echoed by Participant 3, who noted, "The joy comes from teaching my students how to be resourceful and seeing them overcome their own challenges." For PWD teachers, their ability to positively influence the lives of their students is a source of immense fulfilment. Participant 3 elaborated, "Teaching gives me purpose despite my disability. It brings me immense joy to see my students happy." This sense of purpose often compensates for the difficulties they face due to their disabilities.

Additionally, the theme of Gratitude for Acceptance underscores the importance of feeling supported and valued within the school community. Many teachers expressed appreciation for the respect and recognition they received from their colleagues. Participant 2 stated, "One of my joys is connecting with my students and making a real impact on their lives, despite my own struggles." Similarly, Participant 4 shared, "My greatest joy is knowing that my students are learning and growing with me despite my disability." This acceptance fosters a sense of belonging and reduces feelings of isolation, empowering PWD teachers to continue in their roles. Moreover, the collective experiences reveal that a supportive environment not only validates the contributions of PWD teachers but also creates opportunities for shared learning and collaboration between staff members.

According to Rahal (2010), motivation is based on desires, opportunities, and expectations. Moreover, Apolline (2015) and Oyugi (2014) stressed out that motivation can be a very powerful tool for managers and administrators in increasing the commitment and improvement of the employees. In addition, Rakim (2024) pointed out that parents' attitudes, students' attitudes, and the attitude of the community towards teachers are very, if not finally, influential in motivating and making effective teachers.

As such, it is the joy and sense of mission in their work that explains the commitment of teachers with disabilities. The fact that they can be productive even when faced with physical and emotional stress speaks volumes about the benefits of an inclusive and supportive school.

Relevant Theme 2: Struggles and Challenges

While the joys and rewards of teaching are significant, the participants also faced substantial challenges. The theme of Struggles and Challenges highlights the obstacles that PWD teachers face, particularly those related to their disabilities. Two clustered themes emerged: Physical Limitations and Emotional and Social Struggles. These themes were drawn from initial experiences such as "Difficulty in performing physical tasks" and "Social isolation and feelings of invisibility."

One of the most common struggles mentioned by the participants is the physical limitations imposed by their disabilities. Participant 3 discussed, "Having only one hand limits my ability to demonstrate certain tasks, such as writing on the board or distributing materials." Similarly, Participant 5 shared, "Because I have limited mobility with one leg, it can be hard to move quickly around the classroom or stand for long periods of time. This can be tiring and makes it difficult to reach certain areas of the classroom." These physical limitations require significant adaptation and creativity to ensure effective teaching. Participants highlighted how simple tasks, such as organizing classroom materials or managing physical activities, require additional effort, often leading to fatigue and frustration.

In addition to physical challenges, emotional and social struggles were also significant. Participant 2 expressed, "The sorrow comes when there are days I feel invisible, like my disability limits my capacity to perform at my best." This theme reflects the emotional toll of being a PWD teacher, where feelings of inadequacy, frustration, and isolation can emerge when teachers are unable to meet the high expectations placed upon them due to physical limitations.

What the participants in the study went through is consistent with the twin concepts of teachers with disabilities, focusing on the challenges they encounter – physical, emotional, and systemic, that make working in the classroom a working nightmare. Ware et al. (2022) who argued that teachers with disabilities who are working in England have a big problem because there are no policies to support and assist them at the working place.

Ware et al. (2022) informed however that, even though there was active discourse concerning inclusive education for the students, there was no inclusion for the teachers themselves. According to their study, 90% of the teachers with disabilities reported that they were discriminated against and the onus on how to deal with discrimination was on the teachers; accommodations had to be made by individuals but the system which should have been responsible for them remained intact. Such systematic negligence explains the grievances that Participant 3 and Participant 5 raised concerning extra work they experience because they had to modify ways of teaching their students because of their disability.

Also, two feelings stated by Participant 2, where Participant 2 said to have felt "invisible" and where disability was described as what made it a struggle, concurs with the findings of Tal-Alon and Shapira-Lishchinsky (2019). Their work from Israel confirmed that "when trying to deal with the school it is often more stressful than dealing

Relevant Theme 3: Hopes for the Future

The theme of Hopes for the Future captures the aspirations of PWD teachers regarding their work environment and the broader education system. This theme reflects both their desire for personal growth and the systemic changes needed to improve the lives of PWD teachers. Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Desire for Accessibility and Inclusive Future Vision. These themes were derived from initial concepts such as "Hope for more awareness and accommodations" and "Vision for equal opportunities for PWD teachers."

Many participants expressed a strong desire for greater accessibility and inclusivity in schools. Participant 1 emphasized, "I hope for more awareness and accessibility in schools. I dream of a future where PWD teachers have equal opportunities to thrive and that the school environment adapts to our needs rather than forcing us to constantly adjust." Similarly, Participant 5 shared, "I envision a future where teachers with disabilities can work in any school setting without worrying about the physical limitations." Their hopes reflect a

desire for a more inclusive educational system where PWD teachers are fully supported and provided the resources they need to thrive. Participant 2 added, "My vision is a society where PWD teachers are not only accepted but celebrated for their unique strengths."

The concept of an Inclusive Future Vision focuses on the broader changes needed to create an equitable educational environment for all teachers. Participant 4 noted, "I dream of a future where all schools in the Philippines are inclusive, where PWD teachers are not only accepted but celebrated for their unique contributions to education." This vision emphasizes the need for societal change to foster an environment where PWD teachers are not viewed as individuals who require pity or charity, but as essential, valued contributors to the educational community. The participants' collective aspirations underline the importance of systemic advocacy for accessible infrastructure, updated policies, and a culture of inclusion within educational institutions.

The aspirations expressed by the participants are consistent with already existing literature that shows the need for provision and inclusion of teachers disabled. Ware et al. 2022 observed a situation where even if there was talk of inclusive approaches of education in the school, such a practice was not true for teachers. In their study, 9 out of 10 teachers reported being discriminated and the burden of accommodating was placed on the teachers rather than the systemic barriers. Tal-Alon and Shapira-Lishchinsky 2019 appear to concur with this finding when they said "the problem of dealing with the school environment is often more complex and more challenging than coping with the disability". This implies that teachers who have disabilities cope with a lot of external factors such as lack of support, lack of infrastructure and lack of accommodation.

Relevant Theme 4: Challenges in the Workplace

The theme of Challenges in the Workplace refers to the external barriers that PWD teachers face within their school environments. These include both physical barriers and a lack of proper support or resources. Two clustered themes emerged: Physical Barriers and Lack of Proper Support. These themes were derived from initial ideas such as "Inadequate physical infrastructure" and "Lack of training and resources."

Physical inaccessibility was a major concern among participants. Participant 5 shared, "The difficulty I face navigating around the school grounds and sometimes not feeling included in activities." Similarly, Participant 3 discussed the challenges of performing tasks that require two hands, such as cutting materials or conducting physical demonstrations. He said, "There are certain hands-on activities that require two hands, like cutting materials or conducting physical demonstrations, which I need to adjust or simplify."

Moreover, participants also noted the lack of support and resources within the workplace. Participant 4 emphasized, "I think it would be incredibly helpful to have more professional development on creating accessible teaching environments." The lack of adequate training, support, and resources often leaves PWD teachers feeling unsupported, further exacerbating the challenges they face. Participant 1 highlighted, "It would make a big difference if schools were equipped with simple adjustments like ramps, elevators, and ergonomic furniture, which would remove many of the daily obstacles we encounter." These insights suggest that a concerted effort by school administrators and policymakers is required to address these challenges effectively.

A considerable body of research attests to the fact that better resources and accommodation indeed qualify as needs. According to Paul (2015), teachers require a fully equipped facility to reap the dividends because not only do teachers benefit from it but also it is a contribution to improved student outcomes. Such accessibility avails the teachers with disabilities the maximum opportunity to perform their duties more excellently and makes them part of a more inclusive and productive learning environment. Just as Delacruz (2016) has said, lack of instructional materials or deliberately keeping persons from access to educational resources frustrates the purposes of education. Teachers with disabilities necessarily have to face several barriers in performing their duties without proper access to resources, thus affecting the learning experience of their students.

Relevant Theme 5: Opportunities and Growth

Despite the challenges, many PWD teachers view their disabilities as opportunities for personal and professional growth. This theme underscores how PWD teachers use their experiences to enhance their teaching practices and foster a positive, inclusive classroom environment. Two clustered themes emerged: Adaptability and Empathy in Teaching. These themes were derived from initial concepts like "Learning to be more resourceful" and "Improved patience and understanding."

Many PWD teachers have developed creative strategies to overcome their physical limitations. Participant 3 shared, "I've become better at delegating tasks to students, turning it into a learning opportunity for them." Similarly, Participant 2 mentioned, "Having this challenge has made me more creative in my approach. I have developed strategies for class management, such as frequent check-ins and verbal confirmations, to ensure students are staying engaged." These strategies demonstrate how PWD teachers can turn their struggles into opportunities for personal growth and enhanced teaching practice. This adaptability is not only a testament to their resilience but also a valuable lesson for their students in overcoming challenges.

The theme of Empathy in Teaching was also significant. Participant 1 reflected, "My blindness has made me more empathetic. I try to be more patient and accommodating." The ability to connect with students on a deeper level and understand their struggles is an essential aspect of being an effective teacher, and PWD teachers' own experiences with adversity enhance their capacity for empathy. Participant 5 echoed this sentiment, stating, "I've learned to view challenges as opportunities to build a more compassionate and understanding classroom environment." The participants' stories collectively illustrate how their disabilities have become an integral

part of their identity as educators, enriching their teaching philosophy.

A related concept that sheds further light on the importance of this topic is innovative teacher behavior. Thurlings, Evers, and Vermeulen (2015) explain that this is “a process in which new ideas are generated, created, developed, applied, promoted, realized, and modified by employees in order to benefit role performance” (p. 1).

The stories of the participants suggest that their disabilities are not barriers but rather integral aspects of their identity as educators. By embracing their limitations and leveraging their unique perspectives, they enrich the educational experiences of their students. Thurlings, Evers, and Vermeulen's (2015) framework of innovative teacher behavior further supports this idea, emphasizing how new strategies and approaches are essential for professional growth and role fulfilment. The participants' adaptive strategies and empathetic outlook illustrate how PWD teachers embody these principles, demonstrating the transformative potential of adversity in fostering professional excellence.

Relevant Theme 6: Recommendations for Support

The theme of Recommendations for Support encompasses the ideas and suggestions provided by PWD teachers for improving their work environment. These recommendations focus on providing better resources, assistive technologies, and systemic changes at the school, district, and national levels. Two clustered themes emerged: Provision of Resources and Training and Systemic Changes. These themes were derived from initial concepts like "Need for assistive devices and technology" and "Need for policy changes at school, district, and national levels."

Several participants emphasized the need for more accessible resources, such as adaptive tools, voice-to-text systems, and specialized software. Participant 3 suggested, "It would help if schools had more assistive devices like specialized keyboards or voice-activated software to support teachers with physical impairments." Participant 4 added, "Districts should conduct an audit of existing infrastructure to ensure that teachers with disabilities have accessible workspaces, not just students." Participant 2 emphasized the need for training programs, stating, "Workshops on inclusive teaching strategies would be invaluable for both teachers with disabilities and their colleagues."

These recommendations underscore the importance of providing teachers with the necessary tools and resources to succeed and ensuring that educational institutions are equipped to meet the needs of PWD teachers. Beyond resources, systemic changes at the policy level—including advocacy for inclusive hiring practices and comprehensive disability awareness programs—can create a lasting impact. Participant 1 noted, "With the right tools and an inclusive mind-set, we can shift the narrative for PWD teachers and empower them to reach their full potential."

These challenges and solutions are consistent with existing research that underscores the importance of resources and infrastructure in education. Paul (2015) demonstrated how well-equipped facilities positively influence teachers' capacity to fulfil their roles and improve students' academic outcomes. Similarly, Delacruz (2016) argued that a lack of instructional resources undermines the goals of education, further emphasizing the need for targeted investments in accessible tools and training. Subrayen and Suknunan (2019) from South Africa and Haselden et al. (2007) from the USA further emphasize the significance of teacher training and preparation. They highlighted the importance of mentoring programs and learning communities during teacher practicums and internships as foundational for building competence and confidence among teachers with disabilities.

Conclusions

The lived experiences of PWD teachers in public schools revealed both the challenges they face and their ability to persevere. Key conclusions drawn from this study include:

PWD teachers play an essential role in shaping inclusive education, despite their physical, visual, or mobility limitations.

The challenges faced by PWD teachers, including physical barriers, limited resources, and inadequate infrastructure, significantly impact their ability to deliver quality education.

The resilience of PWD teachers is evident in their use of assistive technologies and collaborative teaching methods. They adapt to their circumstances and continue to inspire their students and colleagues.

There is a strong desire among PWD teachers for systemic changes to create a more inclusive and equitable educational environment, with accessible infrastructure, adequate resources, and equal opportunities for professional development.

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